

1 **OPINION**

2 **Multiple circumstantial pieces of evidence point towards a plausible lab origin of SARS-**
3 **CoV-2**

4 Monali C. Rahalkar^{1*} and Rahul A. Bahulikar²

5 ¹C2, Bioenergy group, MACS Agharkar Research Institute, G.G. Agarkar Road, Pune 411004,
6 Maharashtra, India

7 ²BAIF Development Research Foundation, Central Research Station, Urulikanchan, Pune
8 412202

9 Tel: +91-20-25325119

10 *Corresponding author: monalirahalkar@aripune.org

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23

24 **Introduction**

25 COVID-19 pandemic has been devastating not only for human life and health but has almost
26 turned the world upside down for most of us. With the new variants like Omicron we are now
27 in the third year of the pandemic, and there are no signs of its decline so far. After two full
28 years, a huge question remains: how did COVID-19 start in Wuhan, China, and what is the
29 origin of SARS-CoV-2? Initially, the Wuhan seafood market was claimed to be the starting
30 point, but later on, it was proved to be not the source as stated by George Gao, China CDC
31 Director ([https://nypost.com/2020/05/27/wuhan-wet-market-is-victim-of-coronavirus-](https://nypost.com/2020/05/27/wuhan-wet-market-is-victim-of-coronavirus-outbreak-chinas-cdc/)
32 [outbreak-chinas-cdc/](https://nypost.com/2020/05/27/wuhan-wet-market-is-victim-of-coronavirus-outbreak-chinas-cdc/)). There are two main hypotheses regarding the origin of the COVID-19
33 pandemic. The zoonosis hypothesis proposes that the progenitor of SARS-CoV-2 jumped from
34 a bat or intermediate host to a human. This scenario requires that the infected bat or an
35 intermediate host came into close contact with a human in non-research setting which allowed
36 the transmission to occur. The contrasting lab leak hypothesis proposes that SARS-CoV-2 was
37 transmitted into the human population from a research-related activity such as a laboratory
38 experiment. Wuhan city has three big research institutes working on coronaviruses, including
39 the topmost institute researching on coronaviruses is the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV).
40 WIV is the most prominent research institute globally, working on collecting, studying, and
41 manipulating bat-borne SARS-like coronaviruses. Shi Zhengli, the principal scientist, worked
42 for more than 18 years on the collection, sequencing, and genetic manipulation of SARS-like
43 coronaviruses brought from the hotspots, Yunnan and Guangdong. Apart from WIV, Wuhan
44 University and Wuhan CDC located in Wuhan also work on similar aspects and also collect a
45 large number of samples containing coronaviruses. As the pandemic COVID-19 started as
46 pneumonia of unknown etiology in Wuhan, later on, attributed to a SARS-like coronavirus and
47 the laboratories including WIV are in Wuhan, it was an obvious thought in many that the virus
48 could have leaked from a laboratory. Also, the presence of a unique cleavage site, the furin

49 cleavage site in the SARS-CoV-2 genome, which is not present in other SARS-like
50 coronaviruses, was found to be unusual and had rare codon usage (Segreto and Deigin, 2020).

51 **The earliest papers on the origins shaped the narrative: zoonotic origin of SARS-CoV2**

52 The earliest note on looking for the origins of SARS-CoV-2 was published on the 31st of Jan
53 2020, an article by Jon Cohen [https://www.science.org/content/article/mining-coronavirus-](https://www.science.org/content/article/mining-coronavirus-genomes-clues-outbreak-s-origins)
54 [genomes-clues-outbreak-s-origins](https://www.science.org/content/article/mining-coronavirus-genomes-clues-outbreak-s-origins). The critical points of his report were: “It was thought that
55 there was a single introduction into humans and then human-to-human spread, as told by Trevor
56 Bedford, a bioinformatics specialist at the University of Washington and Fred Hutchinson
57 Cancer Research Center. The article further mentioned how Peter Daszak and Shi Zhengli’s
58 group have for eight years been trapping bats in caves around China to sample their feces and
59 blood for viruses. In this article, it was mentioned that they had sampled more than 10,000 bats
60 and 2000 other species. The article also mentioned about 500 novel coronaviruses, about 50 of
61 which fall relatively close to the SARS virus on the family tree, including RaTG13—which
62 was fished out of a bat fecal sample they collected in 2013 from a cave in Mojiang in Yunnan
63 province.”

64 After the publication of this article in Science on the 31st of Jan 2020, on the following day,
65 an emergency teleconference took place on 1st February 2020 where many experts assembled
66 or were invited to discuss the virus's origins. Though it is not still clear what exactly was
67 discussed in the teleconference, recent email redactions
68 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/21177759-house-oversight-letter-and-email-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/21177759-house-oversight-letter-and-email-transcriptions)
69 [transcriptions](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/21177759-house-oversight-letter-and-email-transcriptions) had indicated many facts. The first impression of these scholars was that the
70 virus showed unnatural features (FCS and RBD) and signs of lab engineering. The scientists
71 present in the discussion were top-class virologists and epidemiologists, including Anthony
72 Fauci, Jeremy Farrar, Bob Garry, Francis Collins, Edward Holmes, Marion Koopmans, Ron
73 Fouchier and other researchers and experts. The email discussions indicated that most of them

74 reasonably supported the lab-related hypothesis (70:30, 60:40, 50:50, lab: natural origin), etc.
75 However, immediately following the conference, within the next few days, five of the experts,
76 four of whom were present in the teleconference (Kristian Andersen, Edward Holmes, Andrew
77 Rambaut, and Robert Garry), came together to write a paper stating that SARS-CoV-2 has
78 natural origins (Andersen et al., 2020). The opinion article was available online on the 16th of
79 Feb 2020 and was formally published in Nature Medicine on 17th March 2020, and is still one
80 of the most popular articles on SARS-CoV-2 origins. This paper clearly says that: “Although
81 the evidence shows that SARS-CoV-2 is not a purposefully manipulated virus, it is currently
82 impossible to prove or disprove the other theories of its origin described here. However, since
83 we observed all notable SARS-CoV-2 features, including the optimized RBD and polybasic
84 cleavage site, in related coronaviruses in nature, we do not believe that any type of laboratory-
85 based scenario is plausible.” At the same time, a letter appeared in Lancet on the 18th of Feb
86 2020, where 27 scientists published a research note strongly condemning the “conspiracy
87 theories” surrounding the origin of the virus and supported the Chinese scientists and health
88 workers (Calisher et al., 2020). The Lancet note was co-authored and later found to be
89 organized by Peter Daszak, head of the Eco Health Alliance, EHA, an NGO that collaborated
90 with WIV in the last 17 years. Later on, by redacted emails, it was clear that this note was
91 orchestrated by Peter Daszak, EHA, to push the natural origin narrative. These publications
92 were responsible for shaping a general opinion that the virus had natural origins (Andersen et
93 al., 2020; Calisher et al., 2020). There was no immediate investigation of Wuhan laboratories,
94 and only after one year, a WHO convened joint study mission visited WIV and some of the
95 laboratories (Organization, 2021a).

96 **Lab leak is a possible-plausible theory though discussed only by a few in 2020**

97 It is a well-known fact that WIV, Wuhan, is the world's most famous institute collecting and
98 working on coronaviruses and especially SARS-like coronaviruses. WIV was working on

99 multiple projects aided by the Chinese government, and also in collaboration with Ecohealth
100 Alliance (EHA) and within the framework of several international research programs such as
101 PREDICT, etc. The laboratory collected thousands of bat fecal samples from remote places
102 (Yunnan, Guangdong, and other regions) for isolation, identification, and genetic engineering
103 of SARS-like coronaviruses (Ge et al., 2016; Hu et al., 2017; Latinne et al., 2020). Also, the
104 laboratory of Ralph Baric in North Carolina has been a pioneer in the genetic manipulation and
105 engineering of coronaviruses and especially SARS-like coronaviruses since many years and
106 has collaborated with WIV for the same (Menachery et al., 2015). And hence, as a first step,
107 there should had been an immediate forensic investigation of all the laboratories in Wuhan
108 (WIV, WU and Wuhan CDC) where the outbreak happened, followed by the collaborator
109 laboratories in China and elsewhere. This should have included a proper forensic investigation
110 including detailed and focused interviews of the laboratory staff involved, scrutiny of their lab
111 books, computers, and project reports in the past 15 years. However, none of this followed for
112 a complete year, Jan 2020-Jan 2021. No papers were published that discussed the plausibility
113 of the lab origin of the virus appearing in any of the publications in early 2020. One reason
114 could be because of the impact of Nature Medicine paper and especially the letter in the famous
115 Lancet journal which labeled all the people who thought about the possibility of lab origin or
116 other than the natural origin of the virus as conspiracy theorists (Calisher et al., 2020). China
117 had also issued orders against publishing any paper on origins without permission and
118 publication of research into the origins of Covid-19 would need approval from the science and
119 technology ministry [https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/apr/11/china-clamping-down-](https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/apr/11/china-clamping-down-on-coronavirus-research-deleted-pages-suggest)
120 [on-coronavirus-research-deleted-pages-suggest](https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/apr/11/china-clamping-down-on-coronavirus-research-deleted-pages-suggest). Hence, publications discussing the possibility
121 of laboratory origin of SARS-CoV-2 were very few or redacted in 2020. E.g. The preprint
122 entitled “The possible origins of 2019-nCoV coronavirus” by Botao Xiao and Lei Xiao was
123 posted on Research Gate but was retracted. This pre-print said that circumstantial evidences

124 indicated that the virus leaked from the Wuhan CDC laboratory, which was just a few meters
125 away from the Hunan seafood market, which was initially thought to be the place for the
126 outbreak.

127 One of the first papers discussed how serial passaging of a SARS-like virus in hosts or cells
128 lines could result in the identical genetic signatures left behind as a natural jump from species
129 in a shorter time (Sirotkin and Sirotkin, 2020a). Segreto and Deigin, discussed how the two
130 main features of the virus, the furin cleavage site and the receptor-binding domain looked
131 unnatural and suggested that this could be due to genetic manipulation (Segreto and Deigin,
132 2020; 2021). Further, in a review (Kaina, 2021), the following three scenarios were discussed
133 in detail a. Intentional construction through genetic manipulation, b. the intentional selection
134 in a test animal or *in-vitro*, and c. accidental evolution and human adaptation of the virus in the
135 laboratory. It was also known that various kinds of human cell lines were being used for viral
136 propagation. Hence Kaina (2021) postulated that under conditions of in-vitro propagation or
137 culturing of a progenitor virus of SARS-CoV-2, e.g., RaTG13 and a MERS-CoV, there is a
138 possibility of a virus that gains functions and increases its infection rate in-vitro. Another paper
139 (Segreto et al., 2021b) systematically discusses the flaws in the Andersen et al. paper (Andersen
140 et al., 2020). It outlines how all the pointers authors claimed as proofs for only natural origin
141 are not satisfactory. These include the abnormal codons in the furin cleavage site (FCS). Also,
142 they discussed that the not-so-optimal nature of the FCS and the lack of the progenitor strain
143 could not imply that SARS-CoV-2 had a natural origin. Recently, two reviews have harped on
144 many of these points, pointing to the unresolved question of how SARS-CoV-2 originated and
145 that the laboratory origin could be a strong possibility (Balaram, 2021; Domingo, 2021a; b;
146 Kaina, 2021).

147 Much of that work published on bat coronaviruses in WIV appears to have taken place in BSL-
148 3 labs and BSL-2 labs as per various sources (Zeng et al., 2016,

149 [https://usrtk.org/biohazards/wuhans-lower-biosafety-level-labs-posed-greater-risk-for-
151 coronavirus-lab-leak/](https://usrtk.org/biohazards/wuhans-lower-biosafety-level-labs-posed-greater-risk-for-
150 coronavirus-lab-leak/) and [https://www.science.org/pb-
153 assets/PDF/News%20PDFs/Shi%20Zhengli%20Q&A-1630433861.pdf](https://www.science.org/pb-
152 assets/PDF/News%20PDFs/Shi%20Zhengli%20Q&A-1630433861.pdf)). This makes the
154 laboratory origin hypothesis stronger as the level of safety of the S2 laboratory is much lower
155 for containing highly contagious respiratory pathogens. Many scientists, including Ian Lipkin,
156 who was the paper's co-author, later expressed their concerns about the low safety levels being
157 used.

158 The WHO-China joint team report published on the 30th of Mar 2020 ruled out the possibility
159 of SARS-CoV-2 coming out of any laboratories and labeled it as ‘an extremely unlikely
160 hypothesis’ (Organization, 2021a). However, just after that, the WHO director, Dr. Tedros, had
161 also said that all hypotheses regarding the origins are open (Organization, 2021b). Also, it is a
162 fact that the WHO-China joint team had just spent a few hours in WIV and probably did not
163 visit the other laboratories in Wuhan, such as the labs of the Wuhan University, etc. To date,
164 after two whole years, there are no direct proofs for the virus to be completely zoonotic as
165 discussed in (Segreto et al., 2021); further, no intermediate hosts have been identified, and
166 more than 80,000 animals tested were negative for SARS-CoV-2 (Organization, 2021a). The
167 Biden administration had ordered a ninety-day intelligence probe, though it remained
168 inconclusive, there was one report with moderate confidence pointing towards a lab origin.
169 One I.C. element (FBI) assesses with moderate confidence that the first human infection with
170 SARS CoV-2 most likely resulted from a laboratory-associated incident, probably involving
171 experimentation, animal handling, or sampling by the WIV ([https://www.dni.gov > documents
> assessments \(Unclassified-Summary-of-Assessment-on-COVID-19-Origins.pdf\)](https://www.dni.gov/documents/assessments/Unclassified-Summary-of-Assessment-on-COVID-19-Origins.pdf)

172 In an answer to the two letters published in Lancet by Peter Daszak and co-authors (Calisher
173 et al., 2020; Calisher et al., 2021), a group of scientists had unanimously appealed that there
174 should be an objective, open, and transparent debate about the origins of SARS-CoV-2 (van

174 Helden et al., 2021). To date, no proper investigation has been carried out for investigation of
175 a lab leak of the virus. Our present opinion discusses how various circumstantial pieces of
176 evidences related to the hypothesis that SARS-CoV-2 could have leaked from a laboratory. On
177 the other hand, several indications suggest that the SARS-CoV-2 could have leaked from a
178 laboratory as a natural virus, a passaged virus, or a synthetic virus, and hence it should be
179 investigated as a highly plausible reason (Relman, 2020; Sirotkin and Sirotkin, 2020b; Segreto
180 and Deigin, 2021; Thacker, 2021). Of course, the final answer would only come after a detailed
181 forensic investigation has been done, outlined in an open letter by 31 scientists in the world
182 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.21927.27042/1>).

183 **Collaborative work between China and USA on SARs-like coronaviruses**

184 **The main argument supporting zoonosis and dismissal of lab leak was that WIV or any**
185 **laboratory in Wuhan where the outbreak started was not working with SARS-CoV-2 or**
186 **a closer progenitor than RaTG13** (Zhang and Holmes, 2020; Frutos et al., 2021a). However,
187 in the light of the recent exposure of projects running in collaboration with EHA and WIV,
188 there is a possibility that unpublished strains of SARs-like coronaviruses were being studied
189 by sequencing, and reverse genetics was being used. One of the leading collaborative projects
190 between US-China was an NIH-sponsored project partnered by EHA, WIV, and other partners,
191 entitled “Understanding the Risk of Bat Coronavirus Emergence,” a grant under Award
192 Number: R01AI110964, a five-year project spanning from 2014-to 2019. They focused on the
193 sampling of bats in southern China to identify viral strains with a high predicted risk of
194 spillover. The Aim 3 of the project mainly focused on *“Testing predictions of CoV inter-species*
195 *transmission: We will test our models of host range (i.e., emergence potential) experimentally*
196 *using reverse genetics, pseudovirus, and receptor binding assays, and virus infection*
197 *experiments in cell culture and humanized mice. With bat-CoVs that we've isolated or*
198 *sequenced, and using a live virus or pseudovirus infection in cells of different origin or*

199 *expressing different receptor molecules, we will assess the potential for each isolated virus and*
200 *those with receptor binding site sequence to spill over. We will do this by sequencing the spike*
201 *(or other receptor binding/fusion) protein genes from all our bat-CoVs, creating mutants to*
202 *identify how significantly each would need to evolve to use ACE2, CD26/DPP4 (MERS-CoV*
203 *receptor) or other potential CoV receptors".*

204 **The fifth-year report of the same project documents that they possessed 260 SARS-like**
205 **coronaviruses, and many of the sequences might still be unpublished. The joint paper**
206 **published by WIV-EHA (Latinne et al., 2020) describing the coronaviruses from this**
207 **project had reported only 97 SARS-like coronaviruses.**

208 **Another explanation given by the zoonotic theory proponents is that the chimeric viruses**
209 **were created with WIV1 as the backbone virus, and hence no new SARS-like coronavirus**
210 **backbones could have been used (Holmes et al., 2021). However, the second phase of the**
211 **R01A110964 project indicated that they were planning for reconstruction or synthesis of**
212 **high risks strains.** Additionally, in the extension request submitted in 2018, it was written that
213 there were 50 SARS-like coronaviruses that did not respond to mono-clonal antibodies of
214 SARS1 and were novel. "*Since then, under an R01 awarded in 2014, we have discovered >50*
215 *bat SARSr-CoVs in southern China. Some of these strains can bind to and infect human cells,*
216 *cause SARS-like clinical signs in a humanized mouse model, and evade therapeutic and vaccine*
217 *candidates against SARS-CoV (18). Together these data and analyses will be critical for the*
218 *future development of public health interventions and enhanced surveillance to prevent the re-*
219 *emergence of SARS or the emergence of a novel SARSr-CoV".* The ids, genome information,
220 and detailed list of these more than 50 SARSr-CoVs have not been disclosed in any publication.
221 The proposal for extension of R01A110964 also talks about the synthesis of novel viruses:
222 *'We will sequence full-length genomes of high-risk strains that are antigenically distinct and*
223 *escape SARS cross-neutralization, synthetically reconstruct a small subset (1-2) and evaluate*

224 *the ability of nucleoside analogs to inhibit growth in HAE cultures and/or in vivo (55, 56).'*
225 **The extension project also talks about *searching for SARS-CoVs with 10-25% diverse spike***
226 **(which fits in the current description of SARS-CoV-2, which has a divergent spike**
227 **compared to SARS1** (*"Aim 3: In vitro and in vivo characterization of SARSr-CoV spillover*
228 *risk, coupled with spatial and phylogenetic analyses to identify the regions and viruses of*
229 *public health concern). We will characterize the propensity of novel SARSr-CoVs to infect*
230 *people in vitro using primary human airway epithelial cells and in vivo using the transgenic*
231 *hACE2 mouse model. We will use mAb and vaccine treatments to test our hypothesis that*
232 *SARSr-CoVs with 10-25% divergence in S protein sequences from SARS-CoV are likely able*
233 *to infect human cells and to evade mAb therapeutics and vaccines".*

234 Also, the extended project started in 2019 and continues to date. The extension for
235 R01A1110964 was granted, and the project continued in 2019-2020. The same project was
236 terminated for a short time by U.S. ex-president Donald Trump [https://www.axios.com/bat-](https://www.axios.com/bat-borne-coronaviruses-trump-nih-funding-cut-30f3aac9-39d3-476a-ba8c-e84a8ee87949.html)
237 [borne-coronaviruses-trump-nih-funding-cut-30f3aac9-39d3-476a-ba8c-e84a8ee87949.html](https://www.axios.com/bat-borne-coronaviruses-trump-nih-funding-cut-30f3aac9-39d3-476a-ba8c-e84a8ee87949.html)
238 but then again continued.

239 **Hence, the mere absence of unpublished data does not rule out the existence of such**
240 **progenitor sequences, synthetic viruses, or cultured viruses.** Recently, emails exposed have
241 indicated that the sequences obtained under the R01 or the extension project were withheld,
242 and Peter Daszak did not want to have it published as part of PREDICT program (USRTK:
243 [https://usrtk.org/biohazards-blog/ecohealth-alliance-wanted-to-block-disclosure-of-covid-19-](https://usrtk.org/biohazards-blog/ecohealth-alliance-wanted-to-block-disclosure-of-covid-19-relevant-virus-data-from-china/)
244 [relevant-virus-data-from-china/](https://usrtk.org/biohazards-blog/ecohealth-alliance-wanted-to-block-disclosure-of-covid-19-relevant-virus-data-from-china/)). **Thus, if the above aim (Aim 3) was fulfilled, then it's**
245 **highly probable that high-risk strains which were antigenically distinct and escaped**
246 **neutralization to SARS1 antibodies could have been constructed using synthetic clones**
247 **and then recovery.** Several international programs were going on involving various partners,
248 including common investigators: Peter Daszak, Shi Zhengli, George Gao, Linfa Wang, Ralph

249 Baric, etc. This includes the PREDICT program <https://p2.predict.global/>, global virome
250 project <https://www.globalviromeproject.org/> . These had EHA and WIV as co-partners and
251 very overlapping aims. **Hence, all the data from these projects concerning SARS-like**
252 **coronaviruses should be part of the international scrutiny to unravel the mystery**
253 **surrounding the origins of SARS-CoV-2.** Redacted emails concerning these projects have
254 indicated a strong network within China, Thailand, Laos EHA, UC Davis. In addition to this,
255 a project was submitted to DARPA named DEFUSE
256 <https://theintercept.com/2021/09/23/coronavirus-research-grant-darpa/> by multiple partners
257 (PI Peter Daszak, EHA) also involving Shi Zhengli, WIV, Ralph Baric, and Linfa Wang in
258 2018. Though the project DEFUSE was not sanctioned, the details such as introducing Furin
259 Cleavage sites recovering complete genomes of viruses using human airway epithelial cultures
260 (HAE cultures). A few of the points from the project are: *"The lead organization, EcoHealth,*
261 *Alliance will oversee all work. "Dr. Shi, Wuhan Institute of Virology will conduct viral testing*
262 *on all collected samples, binding assays, and some humanized mouse work." "This will be*
263 *supplemented by characterization of isolated viruses under DEFUSE (at WIV), approximately*
264 *15-20 bat SARSr-CoV spike proteins/year (at UNC, WIV), and >180 bat SARSr-CoV strains*
265 *sequenced in our prior work and not yet examined for spillover potential. We will validate*
266 *results from chimeric viruses by re-characterizing full-length genome versions, testing whether*
267 *backbone genome sequence alters full-length SARSr-CoV spillover potential. Q.S. for full-*
268 *genome characterization will be selected to reflect strain differences in antigenicity, receptor*
269 *usage, growth in human cells and pathogenesis." "We will test growth in primary HAE cultures*
270 *and in vivo in hACE2 transgenic mice. We anticipate recovering ~3-5 full length genome*
271 *viruses/year. "We will analyze all SARSr-CoV S gene sequences for appropriately conserved*
272 *proteolytic cleavage sites in S2 and for the presence of potential Furin cleavage sites".*
273 *SARSr-CoV S with mismatches in proteolytic cleavage sites can be activated by exogenous*

274 *Trypsin or Cathepsin L. Where clear mismatches occur, we will introduce appropriate human-*
275 *specific cleavage sites and evaluate growth potential in Vero cells and HAE cultures.”*

276 **About the importance of RaTG13 and the Mojiang mine**

277 Another point that cannot be overlooked as mere coincidence is that WIV had also collected
278 the closest neighbor of SARS-CoV-2, a virus named RaTG13. WIV had collected a bat
279 coronavirus sample named CoV4991 in 2013, sequenced its RdRp before 2016 (Ge et al.,
280 2016), and the whole genome 2018, and published post-pandemic with SARS-CoV-2.
281 However, in their first publication about SARS-CoV-2, they named this sample as RaTG13
282 without quoting its prior name and reference and declared that they sequenced it in 2020 after
283 they found an RdRp match. Rossana Segreto, in early 2020 observed that RaTG13 and 4991
284 shared the same RdRp and shared it as comments on a virology blog. A doctor, Dean Bengston,
285 published this in a preprint (Bengston, 2020). Picking on this clue, we researched the 4991
286 viruses and found them to be from an abandoned mineshaft in Mojiang. After reading Shi
287 Zhengli's interview (Qiu, 2020) and a paper published in Science, 2014, about the miners in
288 Tongguan, Mojiang, dead due to an unknown virus (Stone, 2014) with a lethal pneumonia, we
289 connected the dots. In the end, we found out that the same mineshaft in Mojiang was the one
290 where the RaTG13 was collected and where the miners had worked to clean the bat feces
291 contracting the infection (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020c). The details of the pneumonia cases
292 were part of a Master's thesis (Xu, 2013) discovered by an OSINT, @The Seeker268. The
293 conspicuous similarities between the miners' pneumonia and COVID-19 prompted us to write
294 the article 'Lethal Pneumonia Cases in Mojiang Miners' (2012) and the Mineshaft Could
295 Provide Important Clues to the Origin of SARS-CoV-2' (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020b).

296 **Miners pneumonia and COVID-19 show numerous similarities: Could RaTG13 or a**
297 **similar virus from the mine be a progenitor or backbone?**

298 In April 2012, six men cleaned an abandoned bat-infested mineshaft in Tongguan Mojiang,
299 Yunnan, and suffered from severe pneumonia followed by hospitalization and death in three of
300 them. One of the most expert pulmonologists in China, Dr. Zhong Nanshan, had remotely
301 observed the two severe cases (patients 3 and 4) and had diagnosed pneumonia to be of primary
302 viral origin, with a high probability. Based on a thorough analysis of the medical records, a
303 medical Master's thesis on these six cases was written by a student Li Xu in 2013. The
304 conclusion of the thesis was: SARS-like bat coronaviruses were suspected to be the causative
305 agents (Xu, 2013). This incident had prompted Shi Zhengli, the principal scientist from WIV
306 working on SARS-like coronaviruses, and her group from the WIV, Wuhan, to inspect the bat
307 coronaviruses in the mine in 2012. However, their paper published in 2016, which is based on
308 the description of coronaviruses from the Mojiang mine (Ge et al., 2016), does not mention the
309 miners' pneumonia and deaths. In a detailed retrospective analysis of these six cases
310 hospitalized in the same hospital in Kunming, we found that the miners' pneumonia mostly
311 resembled COVID-19 (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020b). The analysis was based on the
312 symptoms (high fever, cough, dyspnea), blood reports (low lymphocytes, high D-dimers,
313 elevated SAA, etc.), C.T. scan reports (bilateral pneumonia with ground glass opacities), and
314 the treatment given to treat the pneumonia cases (antiviral, antibiotics, antifungals, steroid, and
315 antithrombotics, in one case) were similar to COVID-19 (Xu, 2013; Rahalkar and Bahulikar,
316 2020b). Another conspicuous similarity between the miner's disease and COVID-19 was the
317 thrombotic complications. The remarkably high D-dimer values indicative of the blood clots
318 are not typically found in SARS, influenza, or other illnesses. As noted by our study and Frutos
319 et al. 2021, almost all the patients showed high D-dimer. Also, all the miners' cases where a
320 fair number of C.T. scans are available (patients 2,3 and 4) show bilateral pneumonia, similar
321 to COVID-19, contrary to SARS1, where the pneumonia is unilateral in 50% of cases
322 (Hosseiny et al., 2020). After looking at the discharge diagnosis of the four serious patients

323 (cases 1-4 as described in the Master's thesis), it is evident that all of them had the following
324 things in common: severe pneumonia, ARDS, and death due to Type I respiratory failure or
325 cardiac arrest and death (patients 1, 2 and 3,
326 [https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html)
327 [Unknown-Viruses.html](https://www.documentcloud.org/documents/6981198-Analysis-of-Six-Patients-With-Unknown-Viruses.html) pages 15, 21 and 33, respectively). All these are in accordance with
328 serious COVID-19 cases resulting in death or long COVID-19.

329 After connecting various dots, our paper also documented the connection that WIV collected
330 several bat fecal samples from the same Mojiang mine, including RaTG13, one of the closest
331 viruses to SARS-CoV-2, with 96.2% similarity at the genomic level. RaTG13 had an older
332 name or id BtCoV-Ra4991 (Ge et al., 2016) not revealed by WIV authors in their first paper
333 after the pandemic (Zhou et al., 2020). Shi Zhengli confirmed this fact in July 2020
334 (www.sciencemag.org, Zhengli Shi Q and A). Also, Shi Zhengli and WIV never revealed that
335 the nearest neighbor of SARS-CoV-2, RaTG13, was collected from the same Mojiang mine
336 where three of six miners died due to a deadly pneumonia illness until our paper revealing the
337 dual connection was published (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020b). Recently, a criticism on our
338 paper was published (Frutos et al., 2021b); however, in our original paper, we have never said
339 that the disease was COVID-19 itself and that the miners were infected with SARS-CoV-2, a
340 fact recently clarified in an article (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2022).

341 The miners' pneumonia and COVID-19 were similar, and RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2 are
342 96.2% identical on the genome level. **Hence further question would be if RaTG13 or a**
343 **similar virus to RaTG13 collected from Mojiang mine be the original virus from which**
344 **CoV-2 could have been derived by serial passage or modification or artificial partial or**
345 **complete synthesis?** The technology of serial passaging as well as cloning the entire virus
346 sequence and retrieving the virus is well known, and such pseudoviruses were being created in
347 WIV (Hu et al., 2017)

348 A preprint published on Biorxiv by Shi Zhengli reveals the collection of eight SARs-like
349 coronaviruses (7909 (RaTG15), 7931, 7905, 7907, 7924, 7952, 7896, and 7921) from the
350 Tongguan mine (Guo et al., 2021). These sequences were briefly mentioned in a collaborative
351 paper of WIV with Ecohealth Alliance (Latinne et al., 2020). Surprisingly, the earlier report
352 (Latinne et al., 2020) did not mention the exact location of the samples- 7896, 7907, 7909, etc.,
353 as the Tongguan mineshaft or even the location, Mojiang was missing. In (Guo et al., 2021),
354 they mentioned that the RdRp of these samples belonged to the RaTG13-SARS-CoV-2 clade,
355 and therefore the whole genome of 7909 was sequenced post-pandemic and named as RaTG15.
356 However, a Master Thesis by Yu Ping, entitled "Geographic Evolution of Bat SARS-related
357 Coronaviruses" (Yu, 2019) guided by Shi Zhengli documented that they sequenced S protein,
358 RdRp, and ORF8 genes from the sample 7909 (later renamed as RaTG15 in 2021).
359 [https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/thesis/ChJUaGVzaXNOZXdTmJAYMTA1MTkSCFkzNjAxMj](https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/thesis/ChJUaGVzaXNOZXdTmJAYMTA1MTkSCFkzNjAxMjc2GghibXV4Mnk0bA%3D%3D)
360 [c2GghibXV4Mnk0bA%3D%3D](https://d.wanfangdata.com.cn/thesis/ChJUaGVzaXNOZXdTmJAYMTA1MTkSCFkzNjAxMjc2GghibXV4Mnk0bA%3D%3D). This study guided by Shi Zhengli involved large-scale
361 detection and analysis of SARS-like coronaviruses from bat samples collected in twenty
362 regions in China from 2011-2016 that were available in the laboratory. In this study, they
363 amplified the full-length RdRp, S and ORF8 genes used for evolutionary analysis and
364 performed whole-genome sequence analysis of some. One of the whole genome sequences
365 obtained was Ra4991, which Shi Zhengli and colleagues renamed as RaTG13 post-pandemic.
366 However, in the May 2019 submitted thesis, its name is still Ra4991. Thus, WIV had more
367 information about the Ra7909/RaTG15 and Ra4991/RaTG13 in 2018, which they did not
368 disclose before. RaTG13 was also sequenced in 2018 itself, as per Shi Zhengli, but in (Zhou et
369 al., 2020), it seems to be mentioned as if it is sequenced post-pandemic. All of the above facts
370 indicate that the details of sampling carried out from the mine were either not disclosed timely
371 or very late. Since the main database describing the information about ~22,000 bat and rodent
372 sequences (<http://batvirus.whiov.ac.cn>) and other details of the collected viruses, is offline

373 since the 12th of Sept 2019 (Anon et al., 2021), the world cannot verify the information. The
374 WHO-China joint team report also lacks the sequence ids or the sequences from the Tongguan
375 mineshaft. A recent report by Jonathan Latham highlights that the phylogeography of the
376 SARS-CoV-2 cluster of viruses hints that the Mojiang mine could be the origin of the
377 progenitor virus of SARS-CoV-2
378 ([https://www.independentsciencenews.org/commentaries/phylogeographic-mapping-of-](https://www.independentsciencenews.org/commentaries/phylogeographic-mapping-of-newly-discovered-coronaviruses-pinpoints-direct-progenitor-of-sars-cov-2-as-originating-from-mojiang/)
379 [newly-discovered-coronaviruses-pinpoints-direct-progenitor-of-sars-cov-2-as-originating-](https://www.independentsciencenews.org/commentaries/phylogeographic-mapping-of-newly-discovered-coronaviruses-pinpoints-direct-progenitor-of-sars-cov-2-as-originating-from-mojiang/)
380 [from-mojiang/](https://www.independentsciencenews.org/commentaries/phylogeographic-mapping-of-newly-discovered-coronaviruses-pinpoints-direct-progenitor-of-sars-cov-2-as-originating-from-mojiang/)). Till 2021, the closest relative of SARS-CoV-2 was RaTG13, 96.2% similar at
381 the nucleotide level and was found at the Mojiang mine in Yunnan Province. They used the
382 Mojiang mine coordinates as the center, as it was the closest. The other following closest
383 genetic relatives of SARS-CoV-2 are RmYN02 (93.2% similar) and RpYN06 (94.48%
384 similar). Latham et al. have shown that these two viruses were both also found in Yunnan, just
385 150 km away (in a straight line) from RaTG13. The following two closest relatives of SARS-
386 CoV-2 were almost equally, RshSTT200 (92.70%) and RacCS203 (91.15%). These two
387 viruses were discovered 1,180 km away and 1,070 km away, respectively. The next relatives
388 were ZXC21 (87.39%) and ZC45 (87.63%). These were found 2,195 km away, followed by
389 C_o319 (79.06%) from Iwate, Japan, 4,140 km away. Beginning from the discovery location
390 of RaTG13, the further away from the mine a virus was found, the less closely related to SARS-
391 CoV-2 it is. Second, the direct bat progenitor of SARS-CoV-2 came from a bat living at or near
392 to the Mojiang mine in south-central Yunnan, China. In other words, the Mojiang area of
393 Yunnan could have been the site of the key zoonotic leap where SARS-CoV-2's ancestor exited
394 its bat reservoir.

395 Recently, a virus closer to RaTG13 has been described from Laos, BANAL-52. The WIV and
396 EHA also gathered their own samples during field trips in Laos and from locations in Yunnan
397 province near the Chinese border with Laos (Latinne et al., 2020). Hence it is probable that

398 these type of viruses were collected by the EHA-WIV team, and more information on this is
399 needed from the concerned people.

400 **Issues regarding RaTG13: could it be more similar or a possibility of a virus more similar**
401 **to SARS-CoV-2 than RaTG13?**

402 As the databases of WIV have been offline since September 2019, and there is no copy of the
403 pre-pandemic sequence of RaTG13 available, we cannot confirm that the Ra4991 sequence
404 and RaTG13 sequence posted post-pandemic are the same or not. Hence, it is a question
405 whether RaTG13 is the true representation of Ra4991 or not. Also, according to a Master
406 Thesis by Ping Yu, 2019, who was Shi Zhengli's student, it is clear that they were still using
407 the name Ra4991. Moreover, it mentions that the whole genome of Ra4991 was sequenced in
408 2018-2019 (Yu, 2019). To date, RaTG13 is one of the closest viruses in terms of the genome
409 and also the spike protein. The protein level similarity of the RaTG13 and SARS-CoV-2 spike
410 is 97-98%. Also, recently a paper has said that RaTG13 could be a consensus sequence (Frutos
411 et al., 2021a).

412 Also there are several basic discrepancies encountered after the analysis of the RaTG13 fecal
413 swab data and other issues (Rahalkar and Bahulikar, 2020a): 1. The genome of RaTG13
414 (MN996532.1) is derived from a fecal swab sample collected in 2013 as per the description.
415 However, the Illumina sequencing entry of SRX7724752 (Feb.13, 2020) is that the sample is
416 recorded as being extracted from a BAL fluid (bronchoalveolar lavage) (Fig. 1).2. Metagenome
417 analysis showed that a large part of the raw data showed low-quality reads (47%), MG-RAST
418 analysis. From the ~53% reads which passed the quality check, 44% of them were contributed
419 by rRNA reads. As MG-RAST does not classify the eukaryotic sequences correctly, we
420 manually blasted the retrieved nucleotide sequences contributed by eukaryotes. Blast analysis
421 of randomly chosen ~150 reads showed similarities to either predicted *in-silico* transcripts from

422 a single sequence (*Rhinolophus ferrumequinum*, MPI-CBG mRhiFer1) NC_046302.1 genomic
423 sequence or to a *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* clone AC155226.4 (~40 kb clone) or other
424 animals in some cases. No sequences showed similarity to *Rhinolophus affinis* sequences.
425 Incidentally, the same group had deposited a *Rhinolophus affinis* anal swab SRA data,
426 SRR11085736 (Figure 2), which would have some sequences from *Rhinolophus affinis*,
427 however we found no sequences directly showing similarities to these reads or any other
428 *Rhinolophus affinis*. Similar discrepancies in the raw data have been pointed out recently
429 (Zhang, 2020). Also, the SRR11085736 data showed 91% bacterial reads, though the methods
430 used for obtaining RaTG13 metagenome SRR11085797 and SRR11085736 are similar (NCBI
431 records). 3. Another major discrepancy is that the RNA sequencing data shows extremely less
432 abundance of bacteria, only 0.7% (according to the NCBI analysis) and similar value was found
433 by our analysis in MG-RAST also. When we compared this to other fecal or anal swabs
434 deposited by the same group, which used the same kits and same methods for RNA extraction
435 and library generation, we found that the SRA data of all of these swabs showed the presence
436 of at least 20-90% of bacterial reads. Bacteria are usually the highest constituents of gut flora
437 and hence contribute to a high extent to a fecal sample. 4. The coronavirus sequence (RaTG13)
438 contributed to ~0.003% of the total sequence reads. A total of 1762 raw reads were retrieved.
439 However, we could not build a de-novo assembly from these reads but only when we used a
440 reference sequence as the whole genome of RaTG13, we could build an assembly. There were
441 less overlaps in a few regions, 2- 3 gaps and a coverage of ~8X. The Wuhan Institute of
442 Virology has recently described methods like probe-capture for getting the whole genome of
443 viruses from samples like bat feces (Li et al 2019). In this case, without the use of any other
444 methods and after using a seven year old fecal swab or fecal swab RNA it is surprising that
445 how the viral reads were of a better quality. 5. No indications of amplicon sequencing have
446 been given by Zhou et al 2020 or in any of the recent publications by the WIV workgroup.

447 Amplicon sequencing files of RaTG13 (SRX8357956) seemed to have been submitted in May
448 2020, but the files have older dates from 2017 and 2018 (Figure 3). 6. RBD of RaTG13 genome
449 does not bind to *Rhinolophus* ACE-2: According to a recent paper, when RaTG13 receptor
450 binding domain was checked for binding with various receptors, e.g. from bats, humans, pig
451 and mouse, RBD, RaTG13 RBD sequence did not show binding efficiency to the tested bats
452 (*R. macrotis* and *R. pusillus*). Instead it showed binding to mouse or rat RBD efficiently (Mou
453 et al., 2020). This is particularly surprising as the virus was isolated from a bat fecal sample (in
454 2013). It has been noted that SARS-CoV-2 has a high nucleotide sequence identity with
455 RaTG13-like virus except for the middle part of its genome encoding the spike protein. Another
456 preprint noted that:(Singla et al., 2020) Evidence for DNA contamination supported by (i) the
457 presence of 98% match with the mitochondrial sequence of *Rhinolophus sinicus* (KR106992.1)
458 which is surprising because a near-complete assembly of a mitochondrial sequence is
459 unexpected from an RNA sample, (ii) the presence of non-adaptor related repetitive motifs,
460 [GGGTTGG(R)AACAGGATA(GGGTTA)_n]m and its reverse complement
461 [(TAACCC)_nTATCCTGTT(Y)CCAACCC]m in a majority of reads. The latter was found in
462 approximately 60% of the dataset, usually on the same end, despite no evidence for these in
463 the TruSeq mRNA kit that was reportedly used.

464 A recent study has indicated that all of the above explanations could be an indication that
465 RaTG13 metagenome data is not from a fecal swab but from a bat cell culture or a tissue sample
466 (Massey, 2021). Steven Massey, a bioinformatician who analyzed the RaTG13 transcriptome
467 data, has clearly indicated that 62.2 % of mapped reads mapped to protein-coding genes. His
468 analyses also clearly demonstrated that the dataset represents a *Rhinolophus* sp. transcriptome
469 and not a fecal swab sample. Therefore, it is a big question about what exactly is the
470 metagenome which had RaTG13? **Moreover, looking at the 98.9% similarity of the**

471 **fragment Ra4991 to SARS-CoV-2 in the 360 bases region, is there a possibility of a virus**
472 **more similar to SARS-CoV-2 than RaTG13?**

473 **Data from the early patients analyzed in WIV adds to the mystery**

474 **Another remarkable fact is that the analysis of the transcriptome data of the early seven**
475 **patients whose samples were analyzed by WIV show cloned fragments of the influenza**
476 **hemagglutinin gene.** We performed a re-analysis of the meta-transcriptome data
477 (SRR11092059-63) generated at the Wuhan Institute of Virology (WIV) from bronchial-
478 alveolar lavage fluid (BALF) specimens of five early SARS-CoV-2 patients
479 (WIV02,04,05,06,07-2) (Quay et al., 2021). The data of these five patients had been obtained
480 by the WIV on two different NGS machines: MiSeq and MGISEQ-2000RS (HiSeq 3000
481 equivalent). Surprisingly, all the five samples analyzed by MGISEQ-2000RS machine showed
482 the presence of a sequence H7N9 Hemagglutinin A (H.A.) segment 4' gene cloned in a vector,
483 in a relatively high proportion, and one case six- times the abundance of the SARS-CoV-2
484 sequences. The presence of non-SARS-CoV-2, including these influenza A genes, has been
485 reported earlier (Aboukheir, 2020). The HA segment four genes cloned in an expression
486 vector, pVAX1. A WIV publication documented that DNA vaccines containing H7N9 HA
487 genes were being developed and tested in mice in WIV at the same time as the outbreak (2019-
488 2020). In addition, all five samples showed a relatively high proportion of *Spodoptera*
489 *frugiperda* rhabdovirus (13-83% of SARS-CoV-2 reads). The presence of cloned H7N9 HA
490 gene segment in the transcriptome data of the early five patients processed in the WIV should
491 be treated as an essential forensic clue and warrants a full investigation. The co-occurrence of
492 vectorized H7N9 sequences with SARS-CoV2 sequences in the early COVID-19 patients
493 BALF suggests that this could be related to a possible laboratory origin of SARS-CoV-2
494 through a lab animal or cell lines which had both of these (vectorized HA and SARS-CoV-2)

495 or leakage of laboratory material through in-appropriate decontamination, etc. We have
496 published the above as a preprint (Quay et al., 2021); however, there is no explanation given
497 by WIV so far, if this is contamination or actual data from the patients' samples.

498 From the presented pieces of evidence, it is clear that there is a strong possibility that SARS-
499 CoV-2 leaked out from a laboratory. Though these are circumstantial pieces of evidence, they
500 pretty much weigh towards a lab-related scenario. Regardless that we get clear proof of a lab
501 leak, the experiments which have been done under various projects to collect, synthesize, and
502 manipulate SARS-like coronaviruses are dangerous enough to create a virus-like SARS-CoV-
503 2. And hence, as a first step, there should be strict international laws controlling all such
504 difficult and risky experiments and research. All such projects and international collaborations
505 should come under immediate scrutiny. All work on native and engineered SARS-like
506 coronaviruses should also be under close international scrutiny, and manipulation of all SARS-
507 like viruses should be stopped. Also, an immediate international investigation under any global
508 umbrella would be the first priority, as outlined in a recent article (Himmel and Frey, 2022).

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